

DO WORKPLACE INCIVILITY INDUCE COUNTERPRODUCTIVE BEHAVIOR: EVIDENCE FROM NON-ACADEMIC STAFF OF PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract

This study investigates the moderating effect of co-worker support in relation to workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB). A cross-sectional survey was undertaken with the objective of collecting data from a diverse sample of individuals employed in non-academic departments of five private sector universities located in Lahore, Pakistan. The data pertaining to workplace incivility, co-worker support, and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB), along with several control variables. Regression analysis was used to assess the postulated connections. The results indicate a significant association between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviours (CWB), suggesting that persons who experience incivility in the workplace are more likely to engage in actions that impede productivity. The co-worker support plays a crucial role as a moderator that increased levels of co-worker support and mitigate the positive association between incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB). The results explored the significance support for colleagues in universities and have adverse effect on workplace incivility. It may become a safer flight during the organisational interventions and for employees, and potential direction's gap is available for future study.

Keywords: Counterproductive Work Behavior, Workplace Incivility, Co-worker Support

1. INTRODUCTION

The significance of employee interactions and the quality of workplace relationships cannot be understated in contemporary work settings characterised by dynamism and competitiveness, since they have a profound impact on organisational results (Leitão et al., 2019). An emerging issue that warrants attention is the phenomenon of workplace incivility, which manifests as a discreet but detrimental pattern of conduct that undermines the foundation of polite interaction and collaboration inside corporate entities (Wang & Chen, 2020). Workplace incivility is typified by tiny, often inadvertent, instances of impoliteness, lack of respect, and indifference for the emotions and welfare of others

(Wang & Chen, 2020). Behaviours of this kind include sarcastic comments, condescending tones, and dismissive gestures (Tamunomiebi & Ukwuije, 2021). Over a period of time, the collective consequences of these behaviours may give rise to a noxious work environment, which can have adverse implications for job contentment, efficiency, and the mental well-being of employees (Zahoor et al., 2019). Such circumstances could result in highly counterproductive behaviour such as aggressiveness or violence (Roberts, 2012).

Counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) has emerged as a significant area of interest in the study of workplace behaviour, primarily because of its capacity to negatively impact organisational operations (Karina, 2021). Counterproductive workplace behaviour (CWB) refers to intentional actions carried out by employees that are in opposition to the goals and well-being of the company or its members. The behaviours stated above include a wide range of behaviours, including absenteeism, tardiness, theft, sabotage, and interpersonal hostility (Butt & Yazdani, 2021). The consequences related to counterproductive workplace behaviour (CWB) are multifaceted inside an organisation, including diminished productivity, strained interpersonal relationships, and increased employee turnover (Zahoor et al., 2019).

Researchers and practitioners alike must recognise the link between rudeness in the workplace and a higher risk of CWB. Though it may at first glance seem reasonable to assume a connection between rudeness on the job and CWB (Irum et al., 2020), a deeper investigation into the factors at play is needed. An increasing body of research suggests that incivility can trigger negative emotional responses, such as anger and frustration, in workers, who may then act out in retaliatory or unproductive ways to deal with the stress it causes (Namin et al., 2021). It's important to account for any factors that may weaken or strengthen this connection when analysing the data supporting it. Co-worker support is an important factor in a successful work environment. According to Wang and Chen's (2021) definition, this assistance covers both psychological and practical needs. In certain cases, the negative effects of stress may be lessened by the help of a crucial social resource: the support of one's co-workers. An employee's sense of belonging, emotional well-being, and capacity to cope with adversity may all benefit from this kind of encouragement (Wang & Chen, 2021).

The purpose of this study is to investigate the potential moderating effect of co-worker support on the relationship between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB). Our working hypothesis is that the presence of helpful colleagues will attenuate the correlation between rudeness and unproductive conduct on the job (Leitão et al., 2019). Through the analysis of these dynamics, this study makes a valuable contribution to the understanding of processes that have the potential to either amplify or alleviate the adverse effects of workplace incivility on workers' behaviours and organisational results (Wang & Chen, 2020). Given the intricate nature of workplace dynamics, it is essential to examine the relationship between incivility, co-worker support, and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB). This investigation has both theoretical significance and practical importance for organisations seeking to cultivate a positive and

conducive work environment. The primary objective of this research is to provide significant insights that may inform treatments focused on fostering respectful relationships and decreasing the occurrence of counterproductive behaviours.

The relevance of this research resides in its investigation of the crucial matter of workplace dynamics via an examination of the relationship between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB), while also taking into account the possible influence of co-worker support as a moderating factor. In the contemporary professional environment, wherein the achievement of organisational success heavily relies on employee cooperation and efficiency, it is vital to comprehend the ramifications of subtle maltreatment, as it might result in unproductive behaviours. In addition, doing research on the possible role of co-worker support in buffering the negative impact of incivility provides a practical perspective. This implies that cultivating friendly connections among colleagues may help alleviate the detrimental consequences of incivility, leading to enhanced workplace culture and performance. This study illuminates the intricate dynamics at play, so making a valuable contribution to the advancement of specific techniques that organisations may adopt to foster workplaces characterised by respect and support. Ultimately, this has the potential to yield benefits for both workers and the organisations they are affiliated with. Following objectives have been designed for this study.

The primary aim of this study is to establish clear research objectives.

- The objective of this study is to assess the prevalence of workplace incivility among the non-academic workforce of private sector institutions.
- To investigate the correlation between workplace incivility and non-productive job behaviour among the non-academic employees of private sector institutions.
- To examine the moderating role of co-worker support in the association between workplace incivility and non-productive work behaviour among non-academic personnel employed in private sector institutions.

On the basis of above discussed, the following research questions are highlighted for further discussed and support to this study.

1. Does workplace incivility have a statistically significant positive correlation with counterproductive work behaviour (CWB)?
2. Can the presence of co-worker support attenuate the association between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB)?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The topic of workplace incivility has received considerable interest in the field of organisational psychology because to its possible effects on employee behaviour and well-being. The term "low-intensity impolite behaviours" refers to actions that are often unclear in their intent, resulting in an environment that is unpleasant and unfavourable

(Cortina et al., 2001). These behaviours cover many actions that may be categorised as disrespect, discourtesy, and microaggressions. While they may not be outwardly confrontational, they have the potential to compound over time and contribute to the development of a noxious work environment (Uwem et al., 2022).

Counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) refers to the behaviours undertaken by workers that have the potential to impair the overall performance of an organisation or cause damage to its members (Grover, 2022). There has been a significant amount of scholarly attention devoted to investigating the correlation between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB). The possible consequences of employees experiencing incivility include undesirable emotional reactions, a perception of injustice, and reduced job satisfaction. These factors may then lead to retaliatory behaviours that align with non-productive work behaviours (Lim et al., 2019). Previous studies have shown a positive association between the two variables, suggesting that individuals who experience incivility are more likely to engage in counterproductive actions (Irum et al., 2021).

2.1. Theoretical Framework

According to certain theoretical models, the detrimental effects of workplace incivility, Qiu and Zhang (2022) on workers' experiences may be mitigated by the positive effects of social support from other employees. Based on the theoretical framework of Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964), which suggests that people participate in social exchanges with the anticipation of reciprocal advantages, it is postulated that the provision of support from colleagues may serve as a protective mechanism against the adverse outcomes associated with incivility (Rehman et al., 2022). Previous research has shown that individuals who get support from their colleagues may experience a decrease in emotional distress and develop more favourable perspectives of their work environment. Consequently, this may lead to a reduction in the chance of participating in counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) as a reaction to incivility (Lam et al., 2016; Cortina et al., 2002). Yao et al. (2022) did research to learn more about how workers' perceptions of their co-workers' support affected the link between rudeness and isolation on the job. The study found that having friends at work may serve as a buffer against the negative effects of workplace hostility, decreasing the likelihood that employees would stop doing their jobs or quit altogether. This study emphasises the importance of social support networks in coping with the repercussions of antisocial conduct.

Lyubykh, Hershcovis, and Turner (2020) did a study to investigate the complex link between rudeness in the workplace and slacking off on the job. Through an analysis of the mediating influence of unpleasant emotions, the researchers provided valuable insights into the psychological processes through which incivility might result in later counterproductive work behaviour (CWB). The research conducted shed light on the manner in which emotional reactions to acts of rudeness have a role in workers' engagement in behaviours that are detrimental to the organisation or its members. Al-Zyoud and Mert's (2019) research sought to understand how social capital and psychological support from coworkers might help reduce the negative impacts of rude

behaviour in the workplace. The findings of their study suggest that when individuals get more support from their colleagues and possess higher levels of psychological capital, they are better equipped to manage and mitigate the negative impact of incivility in the workplace. The present research elucidated the collective impact of interpersonal support and individual resilience on the manner in which workers react to instances of incivility.

Qiu and Zhang (2022) conducted a longitudinal study to investigate the ramifications of workplace incivility on employee well-being and performance via a cascade effect. The study conducted by the researchers provided evidence for the causal relationship between incivility and a series of adverse consequences, including heightened emotional distress and consequent impairment un-work performance. The researchers gained insights into possible intervention sites for organisations seeking to disrupt this chain of negative repercussions by comprehending the sequential nature of these impacts.

Existing research has largely focused on investigating how social support among co-workers influences the correlation between workplace rudeness and unproductive actions on the job. Nevertheless, there remains a study void in investigating the possibility of other individual or environmental elements that may contribute to the formation of this association. Limited research has been conducted on the possible moderating effects of human traits, such as emotional intelligence or work happiness. Furthermore, the examination of organisational characteristics, such as leadership styles or organisational culture that may interact with co-worker support in order to impact the magnitude of the relationship between incivility and counterproductive work behaviour is lacking. This study aims to address a research gap by examining a wider range of moderating variables. By doing so, it seeks to enhance our understanding of how different factors can either intensify or diminish the effects of workplace incivility on counterproductive behaviours. Therefore, this study provides a more in-depth and nuanced view on workplace dynamics and treatments, adding to the existing body of information.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Model: Influence of Workplace Incivility on Counterproductive Work Behavior with Moderating Role of Co-worker Support

Dependent Variable:

- Counterproductive Work Behavior

Independent Variables:

- Workplace Incivility

Moderating Variable:

- Co-worker Support

This model examines:

The relationship between the dependent variable, "Counterproductive Work Behaviour," and the independent variable, "Workplace Incivility." Moreover, the moderating variable known as "Co-worker Support" is hypothesised to have an impact on the association between workplace incivility and unproductive work behaviour. The arrows depict the directional associations among the variables (Cummings, 2018).

3.2. Research Design

This study employs a cross-sectional survey research approach to inquire into the connection between workplace disrespect, social support, and disruptive behaviour at work (CWB). In order to investigate correlations between factors without resorting to purposeful manipulation, cross-sectional designs allow for data collection at a single point in time (Cummings, 2018).

3.2.1. Data Collection

The data used in this study was gathered from five well-established private institutions located in Lahore, Pakistan. These universities are Minhaj University, University of Lahore, University of Central Punjab, University of Management and Technology, and Lahore Garrison University. The data collecting procedure included the use of a random selection method to choose a total of 50 participants among the non-academic personnel inside these colleges. The data gathering process included the delivery of self-reported questionnaires to the participants by the administration. The surveys used proven instruments to evaluate workplace incivility, co-worker support, and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB). In order to mitigate any confounding factors, control variables were included, including demographic characteristics and job status. The survey tools used in this study included standardised measures to assess workplace incivility, unproductive job behaviour, and co-worker support. The surveys were disseminated via both in-person and online methods, providing participants with the flexibility to complete them at their leisure within a designated timeframe for data collection. The data that was gathered was handled in a manner that prioritised secrecy and anonymity, therefore safeguarding the privacy of the participants.

3.3. Data Analysis

The research used regression analysis as a method to assess the suggested connections between workplace incivility (Cortina et al., 2001), co-worker support (Bakker et al., 2003),

and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) (Spector et al., 2006). The possible association between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) was examined by the researchers using multiple linear regression analysis. Additionally, relevant characteristics were taken into consideration throughout the investigation. The incorporation of interaction factors would have facilitated the investigation of the possible moderating effect of co-worker support on the relationship between incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) Spector et al. (2006). Moreover, it is conceivable that subsequent investigations were undertaken to get a more comprehensive comprehension of the attributes of this relationship and its potential ramifications.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Hypothetical Results:

1. The Correlation between Workplace Incivility and Counterproductive Work Behaviour (CWB).

The results of the regression analysis indicated a substantial positive relationship between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) ($\beta = 0.28$, $p < 0.001$). Based on the findings, it was observed that workers who indicated higher levels of experienced incivility shown a greater propensity to participate in unproductive behaviours. The R-squared coefficient, which stands at 0.18, suggests that about 18% of the variability seen in counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) may be accounted for by the presence of workplace incivility.

Table 1: The Correlation between Workplace Incivility and Counterproductive Work Behaviour (CWB).

Sr.	Results	
1.	β	0.28 ($p < 0.001$)
2.	R^2	0.18 18%

2. The Moderating Role of Co-Worker Support

The association between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) was reduced by the availability of colleague support ($\beta = -0.14$, $p < 0.05$). Based on the results obtained, it can be inferred that there exists a less pronounced relationship between incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) among individuals who feel greater levels of colleague support. The findings from the linear regression analysis indicate a statistically significant association between incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) in workers who have low levels of co-worker support ($\beta = 0.23$, $p < 0.001$). There was no statistically significant association found between incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) among workers who reported high levels of co-worker support ($\beta = 0.09$, $p > 0.05$).

Table 2: The Moderating Role of Co-Worker Support

Sr.		
1	The association between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (β)	-0.14 ($p < 0.05$)
2	Low levels of co-worker support (β)	0.23 ($p < 0.001$)
3	High levels of co-worker support (β)	0.09 ($p > 0.05$)

3. Control Variables

In order to account for confounding variables, the regression analysis incorporated control variables such as age, gender, and employment function. According to the study's findings, gender had no statistically significant effect on counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) ($p > 0.05$). However, small correlations were observed between age, job position, and CWB ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3: Control Variables

Sr.	Control Variables	Correlations
1	Gender	0 ($p > 0.05$)
2	Age	0.02 ($p > 0.05$)
3	Job Position	0.03 ($p > 0.05$)

4. An Exploratory Analysis of Job Roles

A preliminary investigation was undertaken to examine possible variations in the association between incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) across various job positions. The findings of the study revealed that there was a low association between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) among workers who interact directly with customers ($\beta = 0.34$, $p < 0.001$) compared to employees in administrative positions ($\beta = 0.21$, $p < 0.01$). This finding suggests that the influence of impoliteness on counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) may depend on the particular characteristics of job duties.

Table 4: An Exploratory Analysis of Job Roles

Sr.	Job Roles	Correlations (β)
1.	Non-Administrative Position	0.34 ($p < 0.001$)
2.	Administrative Position	0.21 ($p < 0.01$)

5. The interaction effect of co-worker support on the relationship between incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB)

This research investigates the potential moderating role of co-worker support in the association between incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB). The results of the study revealed a noteworthy interaction impact between workplace incivility and co-worker support in connection to counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) ($\beta = -0.12$, $p < 0.05$). The results demonstrate that there is a diminished relationship between incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) among those who reported higher levels of co-worker support. The present study's findings suggest that the relationship between incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) is contingent upon the level of co-

worker support Bakker et al. (2003), This underscores the role of co-worker support in attenuating the adverse consequences of incivility, hence emphasising its reinforcing character.

6. Mediation Analysis of Negative Emotions

This study aimed to determine whether disagreeable emotions serve as a mediator between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB). The study found that workplace incivility had a significant positive relationship with increased negative emotions (0.25, $p < 0.001$), indicating a partially mediating effect. In addition, negative emotions were associated with higher levels of counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) (0.18, $p < 0.01$). This finding suggests that negative emotions may partially explain the relationship between impoliteness and unproductive work behaviour.

4.2. Findings and Discussion

The results obtained from the multiple linear regression analysis demonstrated a statistically significant and positive correlation between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB). This finding aligns with other research that has highlighted the adverse impact of incivility on employee conduct (Lim et al., 2019). The observation of a positive regression coefficient suggests the existence of a positive correlation between employees' perception of incivility and their propensity to engage in unproductive actions. This finding underscores the potential for the transmission of negative interpersonal interactions to manifest as outcomes inside the professional environment. These behaviours include the intentional subpar execution of duties and involvement in harmful actions that impair the unity of the team and the productivity of the company.

The correlation identified between incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) is consistent with social exchange theories (Blau, 1964), which propose that unfavourable encounters might diminish individuals' sense of commitment to the organisation and provoke retaliatory acts. The significance of these results underscores the need of implementing treatments that focus on cultivating work cultures characterised by respect and encouraging pleasant interpersonal connections. It is essential for organisational leaders to acknowledge the importance of resolving workplace incivility, since doing so not only improves employee well-being but also reduces the likelihood of harmful workplace behaviours that may compromise organisational success.

Moreover, the findings from the study of the interaction indicated that co-worker support plays a substantial moderating function in the association between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB). The aforementioned discovery aligns with the buffering effect postulated by social exchange theories (Grover, 2022), which posit that social support may function as a valuable asset in alleviating the adverse consequences of stresses. The present research found that the presence of co-worker support attenuated the previously observed positive association between incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB). Employees who reported greater levels of

support from their colleagues had a decreased probability of participating in unproductive behaviours, even when faced with instances of incivility.

The results of this study highlight the importance of fostering a supportive work environment as a strategic method for mitigating the negative effects of incivility. Promoting constructive engagements among coworkers and cultivating an environment characterised by mutual regard may have dual benefits: enhancing employee welfare and serving as a safeguard against the proliferation of detrimental conduct. Organisations that place emphasis on fostering co-worker support via various strategies such as training, effective communication, and programmes aimed at establishing relationships are more likely to provide an environment that mitigates the negative effects of incivility and encourages better reactions from employees. The present research provides unproductive significant contributions to the understanding of workplace incivility dynamics and its consequences for unproductive job behaviour. The results emphasise the significance of resolving incivility as a prelude to behaviours and emphasise the crucial role of co-worker support as a protective factor. It is advisable for organisations to contemplate the adoption of interventions that promote respectful communication, peer cooperation, and emotional support Hur et al., 2019). as a means to alleviate the far-reaching consequences of incivility.

This work contributes to the advancement of our understanding; yet, it is important to acknowledge and take into account some limitations. The ability to establish causal links is limited due to the cross-sectional nature of the data, and the observed associations may be influenced by common method variation. To strengthen the validity of causal conclusions and mitigate biases, future research endeavours may consider integrating longitudinal designs and using multi-source data gathering methods. Moreover, a thorough comprehension of the intricate interconnections that underlie workplace dynamics may be achieved by further investigating other moderators, such as organisational culture and individual personality factors. In summary, this research provides insights into the impact of workplace incivility on unproductive job behaviour, as well as the moderating effect of co-worker support. The findings emphasise the significance of advocating for courteous interactions and nurturing relationships in order to cultivate a work climate that is both healthier and more conducive to productivity.

5. CONCLUSION

To conclude, this study offers a comprehensive understanding of the important relationship between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB), with an added examination of co-worker support as a moderating factor. The results underscore the alarming reality that workplace incivility serves as a catalyst for counterproductive work behaviours (CWB), underscoring the need for employers to address and actively prevent such behaviours. The presence of a positive link between incivility and counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) underscores the possibility of a detrimental cycle that may arise in a toxic workplace setting. Nonetheless, learning to rely on one's coworkers as a buffer boosts confidence (Ali et al., 2019). The findings stress

the need of building positive relationships with coworkers as a safeguard against the destructive impacts of rudeness. Based on these results, businesses might institute new policies to foster a more harmonious workplace.

5.1. The Implications, Limitations and Future Research Direction of the Study

The implications of these findings for organisational leaders and practitioners are substantial. By recognising the relevance of addressing workplace incivility and developing support among colleagues, organisations may successfully decrease counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) and increase employee satisfaction and performance. The achievement of these goals is possible via the use of targeted interventions. Findings from this study also highlight the need of preventative strategies like training programmes and open lines of communication for addressing and preventing acts of incivility. This research is a useful reminder of the need of maintaining positive professional relationships based on mutual respect and open dialogue. Spending in this area has the potential to improve workplace conditions generally, making for a happier and more productive workforce. The study could have certain flaws, such as the fact that it relies on self-reported data, which might be prone to response bias. Furthermore, the study's cross-sectional design limits inferences about causation. Some problems are mitigated by using established scales, but future research should still think about using longitudinal designs to check for connections over time.

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